

Factors Associated with the Performance of Midwives in Support of Exclusive Breastfeeding in the Working Area of the Padang City Primary Health Care, Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Background: The aim of this study was to analyze the factors associated with the performance of midwives in support of exclusive breastfeeding in the working area of the Padang City Primary Health Care, Indonesia in 2018.

Methods: This study used a cross sectional design. The study sample consisted of 64 midwives selected through a proportional random sampling. Analysis of data used bivariate analysis with chi-square test and multivariate analysis used binary logistic test. Data analysis used SPSS program.

Results: The results showed that knowledge, training, workload and attitude of midwife were positively associated with midwife performance. Among the factors, the workload was the most important factors contributing to exclusive breastfeeding. Dominant variable associated with performance of midwives is workload with OR = 2.351.

Conclusion: The conclusions in this study are that there is an association of midwife's performance on workload. It is recommended that midwives improve the knowledge and skills of midwives as supporting performance and evaluating the next Mother and Infant Health service program.

Keywords: Attitude, Knowledge, Motivation, Perception, Performance, Training

INTRODUCTION

One of the health development goals in Indonesia is the achievement of the Millennium Development Goals (MDG's), namely a decrease in infant mortality (IMR) maternal mortality (MMR) through exclusive breastfeeding.^[1]

Midwives as the spearhead of health development that are directly related to public health services can be a supporting or driving factor but can also be a factor in the success of the exclusive breastfeeding program.^[2] The performance of a midwife is also influenced by many factors, namely individual competence, organizational support and management support, this

individual competence is seen in the ability and skills to do work.^[3]

There are three variables that affect a person's performance: individual variables, organizational variables, and psychological variables. Individual factors include: abilities and skills, family background and demographics (age, ethnicity, and gender), and organizational factors include: (resources, leadership, rewards, structure, job design, and factors psychology includes: perception, attitude, personality, learning and motivation.^[3,4]

The International Baby Food Action Network (IBFAN) said that Indonesia was ranked third out of 51 countries in the world

that followed the assessment of the status of feeding and child feeding policies and programs. This shows that breastfeeding as the baby's first food is still lacking.

Breastfeeding support is very much needed because the coverage of breastfeeding is still low, according to United Nations International Children's Fund (UNICEF), the average coverage of exclusive breastfeeding in the world is 38%. According to World Health Organization (WHO), coverage of exclusive breastfeeding in several ASEAN countries is also still quite low, among others, India (46%), Philippines (34%), Vietnam (27%), Myanmar (24%), and Indonesia (54.3%). The coverage of exclusive breastfeeding in Indonesia is still below the 2010 healthy target of Indonesia at 80%. [5]

Providing exclusive breastfeeding in Indonesia to date is very alarming, where people tend to give formula milk when babies are very young. So that it causes many children to lose the opportunity to obtain exclusive breastfeeding, more than 5 million children under five suffer from malnutrition and around 1.7 million children under five experience malnutrition. On this basis WHO recommends that all babies need to get colostrum (early breastfeeding) to fight infection and get exclusive breastfeeding for 6 months to ensure the nutritional adequacy of the baby. [5]

The aim of this study was to analyze the factors associated with the performance of midwives in support of exclusive breastfeeding in the working area of the Padang city primary health care, Indonesia in 2018.

MATERIALS & METHODS

Study Design and Research Sample

The study was conducted using a cross sectional study. The study population were all midwives registered in the working area of Padang City Primary Health Care with 280 people with 64 research samples. The sampling technique in the study was proportional random sampling.

Operational Definitions

The variables in this study consisted of independent variables: individual factors (knowledge and training), organizational factors (infrastructure and workload) and psychological factors (perception, attitude and motivation). The dependent variable is the performance of midwives in support of exclusive breastfeeding.

Data Collection Technique

Data related to research variables were collected through questionnaires with interviews. This study was approved by the Ethical Committee of Medical Faculty, Universitas Andalas.

Data Analysis

The quantitative variables were recorded as frequency and percentage. Hypothesis test used chi-squared test and continued multivariate analysis used binary logistic regression. A two-tailed *P*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. Data were analyzed using the SPSS version 21.0.

RESULT

The performance of midwives, individual factors, organization and psychological respondents can be seen as follows (Table 1).

Table 1: The performance of midwives, individual, organization and psychological factors

Variables	f	%
Performance of midwives		
High	43	67,2
Low	21	32,8
Individual variables		
Knowledge		
High	38	59,4
Low	26	40,6
Training		
Ever	40	62,5
Never	24	37,5
Organization variables		
Facilities		
Good	20	31,3
Not good	44	68,8
Workload		
Mild	41	64,1
Heavy	23	35,9
Psychological variables		
Perception		
Positive	24	37,5
Negative	40	62,5
Attitude		
Positive	37	57,8
Negative	27	42,2
Motivation		
High	25	39,1
Low	39	60,9

Table 1 showed that more than half of the respondents (67.2%) had good performance. More than half of the respondents had a high level of knowledge (59.4%), had received training (62.5%), incomplete facilities and infrastructure (68.8%), had a mild workload (64.1%), negative perceptions (62.5%), positive attitude (57.8%) and poor motivation (60.9%).

Factors related to the performance of midwives in supporting exclusive breastfeeding in the working area of the Padang city Primary Health Care (Table 2).

Table 2: Factors related to the performance of midwives in supporting exclusive breastfeeding in the working area of the Padang city Primary Health Care

Variables	Performance of midwives						p value
	High		Low		Total		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Knowledge							
High	30	78,9	8	21,1	38	100	0,031
Low	13	50,0	13	50,0	26	100	
Training							
Ever	31	77,5	9	22,5	40	100	0,046
Never	12	50,0	12	50,0	24	100	
Facilities							
Good	17	73,9	6	26,1	23	100	0,561
Not good	26	63,4	15	36,6	41	100	
Workload							
Mild	34	82,9	7	17,1	41	100	0,001
Heavy	9	39,1	14	60,9	23	100	
Perception							
Positive	19	79,2	5	20,8	24	100	0,192
Negative	24	60,0	16	40,0	40	100	
Attitude							
Positive	30	81,1	7	18,9	37	100	0,012
Negative	13	48,1	14	51,9	27	100	
Motivation							
High	19	76,0	6	24,0	25	100	0,353
Low	24	61,5	15	38,5	39	100	

Table 2 showed that there were relationship between knowledge, training, workload and attitude with the performance of midwives in support of exclusive breastfeeding ($p < 0.05$). But there were no relationship between the availability of facilities, perceptions and motivation with the performance of midwives in the support of exclusive breastfeeding ($p > 0.05$).

Based on the results of bivariate selection, it was found that all research variables: knowledge, training, workload and attitude produced p value < 0.25 and continued with multivariate analysis (Table 3).

Table 3: Multivariate analysis

Variables	Sig. (2-tailed)	B	Exp (B)
Knowledge	0,056	1,357	3,883
Training	0,256	0,796	2,218
Workload	0,002	2,240	2,351
Attitude	0,054	1,315	3,725

Table 3 showed that the dominant factor with the performance of midwives in the support of exclusive breastfeeding in the working area of Padang City Primary Health Care is the workload (OR 2.351).

DISCUSSION

The results showed that knowledge, training, workload and attitude of midwife were positively associated with midwife performance. Among the factors, the workload was the most important factors contributing to exclusive breastfeeding.

The high knowledge of midwives about the implementation of exclusive breastfeeding programs goes well shows that, knowledge is not a major factor in the good performance of midwives, there are other factors including opportunities to develop skills and government policies to assign midwives to attend seminars or training.

A good relationship between training and midwife performance needs to be done because taking part in the training will give birth to officers who have good service quality and training to provide action to the community especially for breastfeeding mothers, training that must be carried out by midwives is training lactation counselors by following this training, the knowledge gained by midwives is growing.

Excessive workload will cause tension, stress, frequent mistakes, reduce self-confidence, so a midwife is happy to accept additional assignments in addition to the performance duties given, so that motivated midwives themselves do work creatively, calmly and optimally so that the workload is given also goes smoothly then give in the form of rewards.

The relationship between attitudes and the performance of midwives in the support of exclusive breastfeeding is caused by a positive attitude that will affect actions

in doing work and vice versa. Therefore, to improve the performance of midwives in carrying out exclusive breastfeeding, management must be active in conducting guidance and socialization that good nursing mothers will be able to maintain the health of their mothers and children. [6] Previous study stated that if the workload that was received was too large, it would cause work stresses that could affect work motivation and decrease performance. [7]

Based on the analysis of researchers it is known that workload is the dominant factor of performance in carrying out exclusive breastfeeding support. This is because the proportion between the number of staff and the number of midwife programs is not balanced so that one officer can have more than one assignment, therefore the services provided are not maximal especially for breastfeeding mothers.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this study confirmed that knowledge, training, workload and attitude of midwife were positively associated with midwife performance. Among the factors, the workload was the most important factors contributing to exclusive breastfeeding.

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